

Voyage Narrative for the TAN2502 *RV Tangaroa* “ACTUATE” expedition to the Ross Sea¹

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Jan-Feb 2025.

Introduction

The *RV Tangaroa* ACTUATE 2025 Ross Sea Voyage was the ship’s 16th voyage to Antarctica and Southern Ocean. The ACTUATE (AntarCTic soUthern oceAn scienTific rEsearch) voyage was supported by funding from the Ministry of Business, Innovation, and Employment (MBIE), the Antarctic Science Platform (*Fernandez et al. 2025*), NIWA Strategic Science Investment Funds, University of Auckland, University of Otago, University of Canterbury, Victoria University Wellington, and overseas funding agencies (India’s CMLRE - Centre for Marine Living Resources & Ecology; U.K. NERC).

This is the narrative built up from the regular updates sent out every few days to a range of interested parties and formed the basis of the public web blog.

RV Tangaroa just north of Ross Island – Image Rob King.

The science objectives for the 2025 *RV Tangaroa* Voyage included:

1. Hydrographic operations
2. Benthic communities sampling
3. Profiling float deployments
4. Polynya RISIPE (Ross ice shelf front polynya experiment) moorings operations
5. Impact and content generation

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6. Fisheries eDNA
7. Zooplankton monitoring
8. Biogenic Aerosols mapping from underway sensors
9. Ocean surface biogeochemistry
10. Seeps sampling
11. Marine mammal monitoring with hydrophone recorders.
12. Seawater Oxygen sampling

The voyage spent 30 days of the planned 39 days at sea within the Antarctic Treaty area (south of 60°S). *Tangaroa* carried a total of 38 persons, comprising 18 officers and crew, and 20 scientific and technical staff. The voyage started from and returned to Wellington, New Zealand and had a focus on the western Ross Sea continental shelf area. *Tangaroa* departed from Wellington on 14 January 2025 and proceeded directly to the northern boundary of the Antarctic Treaty Area at 60°S, deploying Argo floats and running the Continuous Plankton Recorder (CPR) enroute. Once in the Antarctic Treaty Area, the first voyage objectives were to recover passive acoustic moorings deployed on the Pacific-Antarctic Ridge and Scott Seamount in 2023. The vessel then recovered moorings south of Iselin Bank. From there *Tangaroa* transited towards Cape Washington and moved towards the coast around Wood Bay to begin the first coastal shelf survey. From there further surveys took place at

bon voyage – Tangaroa departing through the Wellington heads. Image: Liv Cornelissen.

Franklin Island, Ross Island, Coulman Island, Cape Hallett, Robertson Bay, Possession Islands and Hallett Ridge. The ship spent around 24 hours at each study area to carry out a multibeam echosounder (MBES) survey, deep-tow-imaging system (DTIS), seafloor sediment and biological sampling, together with CTD casts and incorporated underway and CTD rosette water collection and eDNA analysis. During this time, the team recovered and, in some cases, redeployed oceanographic mooring along the front of the Ross Ice Shelf and in the Cape Adare region. This work became RV *Tangaroa*'s farthest south science activity. In addition, we successfully completed a ten-day glider mission for biogeochemistry/hydrography as well as underway atmospheric and surface water sampling and oxygen isotope sampling from the CTD. On our return transit the ship paused to perform a final deep CTD at around 58°S and continued towed-CPR work until reaching the New Zealand continental shelf.

The Narrative

Underway! 17jan2025

After nearly a year of planning we are finally underway. The crew of RV *Tangaroa* cast off the lines from Burnham Wharf at 4pm (... or 1600 as now everyone is getting used to) on January 14th and we efficiently skirted the tip of Miramar Peninsular, past the Massey Memorial, and out through the harbour entrance – dropping the Harbour Pilot as we went. There is little forgiveness sailing out of Wellington as you go straight into Southern Ocean conditions. We were fortunate that, after ten

days of southerly winds that had seen cancelled ferry sailings and general air of summer complaint all through Wellington, the conditions had eased enough that, whilst not flat, it wasn't carnage.

We now commence the long line south - basically a straight-line south. I gave a departing karakia my best go. It's a good one about the various winds we will encounter. Touch wood but we look to be shooting the gap between two storm systems. When I said that to a media person prior to departure, they were concerned and wanted to know if the storms were unusual. I pointed out it was the Southern Ocean, and so the lull was the unusual thing.

The long transit down gives the team time to get to know the ship, the gear and each other. We have twenty scientists aboard and eighteen crew, so it's a reasonably full ship. Most of the science team share a cabin. The cabins are ok, not large, not tiny but you sure get to know your cabin mate. The ship's crew are putting the team through daily drills so the science team can stay safe in what is a complex work environment.

These voyages are always multi-faceted, so we have several key objectives plus several side-activities. The main work is in three parts – (1) maintaining our heat/salt sensors located at various locations around the Ross Sea, (2) comparing eDNA and acoustics sensing of fish populations and zooplankton and (3) the biggest single task is given over to mapping and cataloguing of seabed plants and animals. On top of that we have smaller projects monitoring the atmosphere as we sail as well as retrieving whale monitoring sensors. The tech is a nice mix of gear that the oceanographer of 1950 would recognise, along with cutting-edge robotics, acoustics and eDNA methods. I'll focus on the teams, Institutes and work as it happens in later updates.

This is the sixteenth Tangaroa voyage to the Ross Sea (*Stevens and Fernandez 2023*). It's interesting to reflect on the evolution of funding over that time as each voyage typically has a primary supporter. There have been voyages primarily funded by things as broadly spread as hydrographic surveying baselines and whale population counts. However, the major supporters over the past decades have been fisheries science, that then evolved into Marine Protected Area research. The last few voyages have seen a steady growth in support from the NZ Antarctic Science Platform which has a "climate in Antarctic and implications for NZ" focus. This looks to be true for future voyages too, along with central Government support for the vessel-time. This enables longer-term planning and means the Antarctic ocean research community can build national and international linkages, as well as the science that comes with that longer-term commitment to data and capacity-building.

Survival suit drill – Image: Nicole Hill.

As I write this, we've just dropped off the southern margin of the Campbell Plateau and so beneath us are currents that are transporting water created around Antarctica a few decades ago that are now working their way past N.Z. and out into the wider ocean. The data we are gathering contributes to Antarctic, Aotearoa New Zealand and global understanding of the changing planet.

Biophysics in the ACC – Jan 20

Not wanting to upset the good luck, but I must say our run South with calm seas has continued. The Antarctic Circumpolar Current (ACC) that we are presently crossing is usually described as being filled

with huge waves and strong winds – but, so far, not this time. This good fortune has enabled us to make an excellent start on one of the newer components of the voyage – work looking at how biology and physics interact at the Antarctic Polar Front.

The Front is where cold Antarctic waters meet the warmer waters to the north and gets described in textbooks with nice bold lines, but the reality is it can be a complex mix of eddies and subducting layers beneath the ocean surface. And this is made even more complex because the Campbell Plateau at the southern bound of Zealandia – the submerged continent that Aotearoa New Zealand is part of – is one of the major pinch points for the Front. So as the Antarctic Circumpolar Current flows to the east it has to squeeze past the Plateau with the result being it gets very messy and nothing at all like the text-book bold line on a map.

This complexity gets amplified when you add in biology and how living things survive in this environment. NIWA's Dr. Alina Madita Wieczorek conceived a pilot experiment to sample biophysical properties across the Antarctic Polar Front with the Conductivity Temperature Depth package (CTD*) and then use eDNA to see if there is a connection between physical structure and measured ecosystem properties when viewed through residual DNA.

This helps us connect between the physical setting, the plankton-filled background biology and the larger fish and marine mammals. Critically, we know that this frontal structure will change with a warming ocean, but not the details of how, or what the impacts will be.

Making way south - Image Ira Cooke

So, it was great to see the CTD come up on deck and the team swarmed around the sample bottles to get processing going – all at 3 am. It is noted the University of Genoa's Marco Grillo gets the MVP award for enthusiastic sampling.

This was immediately followed by Dr. Svenja Halfter's net-tows to get samples of some of the larger species affected by the changing water. The successful sampling made for a nice birthday present for me 😊. The sorting of the sample species ends up looking like a bento box.

[*The CTD "Conductivity Temperature Depth" sampling package is so central to oceanography that I'll devote an entire Update to the instrument, and how the deck and tech teams make this work, once we get more data.]

The work continued as we then hunted for the southern side of the front, and it took much longer than we anticipated. Alina kept a close eye on the ocean surface temperature as it stubbornly stayed warm (~3.5C) but then after twelve hours we sailed

into ~ 2.5C water and we knew we were into Antarctic waters. At that point Alina, Svenja and team repeated the sampling of the previous night – the main difference being everyone was wearing more layers!

Alina's experiment evolved out of the 2024 Joint Italy-New Zealand Laura Bassi voyage, funded by the Antarctic Science Platform, where we got to shake down the approach. Unfortunately, on that voyage the conditions over the Antarctic Polar Front were not good for sampling.

So now, a year later, with the Antarctic Science Platform again supporting a voyage, and additional funding from NIWA's SSIF Strategic Voyage Fund and collaborative support from India's Centre for Marine Living Resources and Ecology, Alina was able to give it a proper go. This is an excellent example of how long-term funding, when sufficiently flexible, allows both certainty and the emergence of new ideas.

There was an additional milestone that was achieved as we sailed south – we “Crossed the Line”. On this ship the line is at 60 degrees south. It is a tradition to award first-timers with a ceremony, costumes and a certificate as they do at the equator (but colder). With a large part of our contingent students, or more used to working further north, we had a good number of first-timers. What I wasn't aware of was that I had to wear a Superman costume.

One of the first icebergs spotted – Image CC BY-NC-SA | Nicole Hill

This northernmost part of our work programme emphasizes the Southern Ocean aspect of the research. It is easy to be captured by the amazing Antarctic scenery and discoveries, but - as our primary strategic guide, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Trade Aotearoa New Zealand Antarctic and Southern Ocean Research Directions and Priorities 2021–2030 document - points out, there are many things about the Southern Ocean still to be determined, not the least of which it is the changes coming for the primary absorber of heat and CO₂ on the planet.

So, we continue south to our next sampling station. Oh, and we spotted our first iceberg!

[The CTD Day – Jan 24th, TAN2502 Update](#)

This update necessarily comes to you hot on the heels of the previous one because January 22nd was CTD Appreciation Day! There are many “world appreciation day for thing X” that are somewhat limited in appeal but CTDs are definitely worth the celebration as they are a mainstay of oceanographic instrumentation and have evolved to be critical pieces of kit for any ocean research.

A CTD – conductivity temperature depth – profiler package is a suite of ocean instruments measuring far more than temperature and conductivity (which gives salinity). Oxygen, light, turbidity, and other data if you have the sensors, are all possible. Decades of development have enabled these sensors to be highly accurate over most ocean conditions. For example, the temperature sensors are accurate to within a few millidegrees! It's a struggle to even find an independent sensor good enough to check that level of accuracy. And yet it can make a difference for how we categorise deep ocean waters, especially as they change with climate.

In addition, the instruments are topped by a carousel of water sample tubes that snap shut at desired depths. This water provides raw material for a whole slew of science from eDNA through to measuring oxygen levels.

So, a “CTD cast” involves careful pre-deployment checks by Dr. Jasmin McInerney, the technical lead for the work. Then the whole assembly is carefully winched over the side, followed by the slow lowering of the package – sometimes for many hours. All the while data come up the wire, and we watch the ocean structure unfold before us. The instrument has a seabed detector, so we know not to crash into the seafloor. As we haul the package back in, we stop at preselected depths to close a sample bottle. Finally, it all comes aboard thanks to the deck crew. It's impressive to watch this team, many with decades of experience of getting delicate science gear in and out of the ocean in all conditions.

When the instrument comes on board, and once the Ship's deck crew have safely secured everything, it looks like a Formula One pitstop as the team gather round to collect samples and check electronics. Indeed, my co-Voyage Lead Dr. Denise Fernandez is first in the queue to grab small vials of seawater (the same size as for a blood sample at the Doctors) that will be processed to quantify the level and origin of oxygen in the seawater. The samples are being collected for U.K. colleague Dr. Kathryn Gunn (Univ. Southampton) who is leading the large international project “FRESH” that seeks to map out the freshwater budget of the Ross Sea. We know the amount of freshwater diluted in the ocean water in the region is important for regional and global circulation, as well as ecology and sea ice formation. However, if we are going to identify how this might change in a warming world we need to know where the freshwater has actually come from – glaciers, sea ice or even submarine groundwater. This is one of a number of international connections happening onboard, reflecting New Zealand's strong presence in the highly collaborative Antarctic Oceanographic research community.

With the many uses of the seawater comes a challenge of course, as each CTD deployment brings back only a certain amount of water, and only from certain depths. One of Denise's (many) key roles on the voyage is to manage the sampling from the CTD rosette so that nothing is wasted and we hit all our target samples.

Given the central place the CTD holds in the voyage, there's a lot of pressure for the CTD to

*Conductivity Temperature Depth (CTD) –
Image: CC BY-NC-SA Denise Fernandez /
NIWA.*

operate in good working order under sometimes difficult circumstances. NIWA's past and present technical teams continue to do a very effective job with the modest resources available to keep this critical infrastructure operating to a high standard. On this trip, Dr. Jasmin McInerney leads the CTD controls with support from technical experts Nick Eton and Jacob Hall.

A profound change has come over most of us aboard in the very short time since the last update - we've crossed the Antarctic Circle. All of a sudden, temperatures dropped off in both the ocean and air, and – and this was a big hint – huge icebergs started to appear. After many years of doing this kind of work, I still take a breath when I see the first few large bergs (and really, these aren't that big – less than 1 km long). I have to say, on this voyage, with a number of people aboard for the first time – their delight and wide-eyed wonder at the sights (there's been sea ice and a lot of whales too) is an absolute pleasure.

From here we head onto the continental shelf and onto a long list of tasks.

Benthic Ecosystems – Jan 27

Apologies in advance, this update is a long one as it describes the most complex sampling effort of the voyage in terms of equipment and people. Since the last update, we crossed over onto the continental shelf and turned westward, picking up moored temperature, salinity, currents instrumentation as we went. After the stunning icebergs and sea ice of the shelf-break edge this middle run was fairly non-descript – a condition that continued as we arrived in the early morning at our coastal sampling station at Wood Bay near Cape Washington. The coast was shrouded in low cloud, and we could only just make out ice, rocks and snow along the shoreline, leaving folks aboard a little deflated about their first view of Antarctica. This all changed rather miraculously mid-morning when the clouds dissipated to reveal the high, rocky headland of Cape Washington itself, and then the stunning Mount Melbourne – an active volcano and something of a Mount Erebus doppelganger.

It was at this point that the benthic ecology team swung into action. Led by University of Otago Professor Miles Lamare and, onshore, NIWA's Dr Vonda Cummings - the team is carrying out surveys and sampling that builds on a number of previous *Tangaroa* voyages. I first met Miles at Scott Base over twenty years ago and he is currently Head of Department for Otago's Marine Science Department. The benthic team were hand-picked by Miles and Vonda - and you wouldn't know it from the seamless workflow, but none of the visitors had met each other before (other than during online pre-voyage meetings).

Samples from RMT net-tows – Image CC BY-NC-SA
Hugh Carter

The critical and unique seafloor ecosystems in the region are highly responsive to sea ice, temperatures and salinity. So, the team have developed a sequence of measurements from acoustic scanning, through to high-definition camera surveys and actual samples of the seafloor, sea life and water. This means the same work package incorporates the latest digital HD video, fibreoptic cable, eDNA, and precision satellite positioning, at the same time as a beam trawl and benthic grab that would have been at home on the back deck of HMS *Challenger* in the 1870s.

The video is captured by NIWA's Deep Towed Imaging System (DTIS) and the data coming up the fiberoptic feed is astounding. Beautiful, clear imagery of the complex seafloor communities and individuals. What is equally impressive is the teamwork between DTIS drivers (NIWA's Nick Eton and Jacob Hall) and the ship's winch operators, in conjunction with several taxonomists working in real-time to identify key moments in the video to return to for more in-depth analysis. To step into the darkened lab to hear combined radio chatter about winches and wire-out in parallel with the rapid-fire listing of species being observed through the video feed is inspiring.

It's fair to say our international colleagues, from India, Australia, Italy and the UK, were all impressed at the quality of the DTIS imagery. Simultaneously, it highlights the vital role taxonomists play in understanding systems and change and the benefits of home-grown technology development.

The remotely sensed acoustic and video data of the sea floor are one thing, but when the benthic grab came on deck and you get to see the samples for real, it is another. All sorts of starfish, sponges, rocks, even fish, all spill out in a riot of colours and shapes and sizes. The video sampling means the physical sampling is as targeted, and minimal, as possible.

Despite this targeted sampling, a voyage like this can collect a lot of samples in a short amount of time, so a good deal of care needs to go into corralling the researchers and sorting the samples. NIWA's Dr. Pamela Olmedo Rojas directs the sorting and storing, as well as monitoring the safe operations of the team in all sorts of conditions. This vital role enables us to come home with a structured set of samples, making the transition to shore-based analysis as smooth as possible.

Equally importantly, we need to know where the samples have come from. So, it was great to have University of Tasmania's Senior Research Fellow Dr. Nicole Hill aboard as she specialises in the intersection between mapping and biodiversity. The importance of the mapping rapidly becomes apparent when one sees of the seafloor gouges where icebergs had simply ploughed through erasing anything that can't get out of the way. Only a few metres apart are communities hundreds of years old, next to an area where everything is less than two years old. Then, in addition to this natural regionality, the work is all imbedded within the Ross Sea Marine Protected Area, the largest MPA anywhere. Clearly, in order to protect something, we need to know what we are protecting and where.

The team on a deployment exercise with Mount Melbourne looming. Image Gert-Jan Jeunen / University of Otago - Ōtākou Whakaihu Waka.

On days when sampling is light, we've been having science talks from various people aboard and we'd been fortunate to hear talks from two of the taxonomic experts, Dr Ira Cooke (Australia) and Dr Hugh Carter (U.K.), about the species they were interested in. So, when the samples we being sorted we all had more of an idea about what was going where, and why. And, as well, we had enhanced respect for the implications of some of the rarer samples. The team are supported by University of Otago students Emma Downer and Fiona Schultz, as well as Italy's Dr. Marco Grillo, who apply themselves

diligently to the many sampling tasks when not looking out for whales, penguins, icebergs, orca and volcanos.

In parallel with all the physical sampling, the voyage has a lot of eDNA (Environmental DNA) work going on. Some rather remarkable techniques have evolved over the last few years enabling the detection of genetic indicators in environmental material like seawater and seafloor sediments. So, the benthic team are rounded out by University of Otago Research Fellow Dr. Gert-Jan Jeunen who diligently appears at regular intervals to grab buckets of water that then disappear for eDNA analysis in a “clean” laboratory container set up high on the port side, back-deck.

If the sea ice ahead lets us, we will repeat this effort at a number of locations, from around 50 metres depth through to over 200 metres deep. The reason we go to all this effort is primarily because it is a unique ecosystem - with the combination of very cold water, sea ice, icebergs and the light regime, as well as relatively little human presence. This whole system lives, and thrives, in a very narrow temperature range, so the potential for major change being caused by a warming ocean and increased meltwater is large. These unique data will help us understand where the ecosystem is at now, and where its headed. What happens in Antarctica, *does not* stay in Antarctica – changes around the southern continent will be felt in Aotearoa New Zealand in the decades and century to come.

From here we turn south for Franklin Island and the Ross Ice Shelf.

Polar Ocean Robotics – Jan 31

All through the planning meetings for the voyage I’d stressed to the team that the plan was all very well, but it was entirely at the mercy of Antarctic sea ice which can change very rapidly. Early in the voyage I got together with the ship’s bridge team, and Ice Pilot Evan Solly – a veteran of many of these voyages south – to look at the various satellite images of how the ice in the region was evolving.

Unfortunately, it was clear that our initial target areas for sampling were going to be filled with sea ice for a week or more, and our best option was to actually reverse the route for the entire voyage. So, after a long night with the scheduling spreadsheet, I had a new plan. So now, upon saying goodbye to Mount Melbourne, instead of the initial route north, we set our compass to the southward.

But before we got going too far, we stopped engines to drop off NIWA’s Ocean Glider Manaia. An ocean glider is a two-meter-long tube stacked with batteries, electronics and a miniature CTD (to measure salinity and temperature). It doesn’t have a propellor though – instead it adjusts its buoyancy so that, with its little wings, it can silently glide through the upper few hundred metres of the ocean, surfacing occasionally to report back via satellite, and pick up any new instructions – essentially a robot. It does all this at a rather leisurely pace, covering perhaps 20 km in a day.

Deploying an ocean glider – Image Svenja Halfter / NIWA.

Dr Jasmin McInerney is aboard Tangaroa for the voyage and, among her many tasks, leads NIWA's ocean glider facility – a programme initiated a decade back by colleague Dr. Joanne O'Callaghan. Jasmin is a veteran of many glider launches, in both Antarctic waters, and other challenging systems and from all kinds of vessels. After our route change, Jasmin and I had to plan a whole new mission for the glider.

After being gently deposited in the water by the deck crew using the ship's crane, Jasmin ran a long list of checks to make sure Manaia was set to go. Ocean gliders are hugely complex with any number of things that can trip up operations and result in a rescue mission for the ship and a lot of wasted time.

Eventually, with the all-clear, Jasmin set the glider on its way. By this time, it was about 2am but she was able to head off to bed because Eleanor Haigh back at the NIWA offices in Wellington took over piloting the glider remotely for the start of its journey north. Eleanor was doing this at the same time as keeping an eye on NIWA's other ocean glider Betty, which is currently working in the Taranaki Bight.

I mention sleep quite a bit in these updates because, with the 24-hour daylight, and the small team with many tasks, it's very easy to run something of a sleep deficit, and fatigue means mistakes get made. In a large vessel with significant resources, you just run duplicate teams around the clock. That is simply not an option for us, so a good deal of our day-to-day planning is around how to maintain the best-rested team.

*Deployment and testing of a BGC Argo float –
Image: Svenja Halfter / NIWA.*

The region Manaia was launched into is called the Drygalski Trough. It's a 500 km long groove in the seafloor, in places over a kilometre deep, that is one of the critical transport corridors for cold salty waters formed in Antarctic coastal regions in winter. This water moves north to the edge of the continental shelf and beyond. Some of the final tasks of the voyage will be to gather sensors measuring this outflow.

As Tangaroa resumed her southward journey, the target was Franklin Island – at around 76 degrees South (140 km north of Ross Island), it looks at first glance a rather unassuming slab of ice and rock. This was the second target area for the benthic ecology group. As we sidled up, the island slowly revealed itself to be full of life with penguins and orca in great abundance. Of course, once we looked a little harder it was clear the orca were chasing the penguins.

After an intense 36 hours for the seafloor sampling team, we again departed – this time heading due east. Our next task was to launch a couple more robots – but a different flavour. Much earlier in the voyage we'd deployed ten "Core" Argo profiling floats across the Southern Ocean. Argo are like an ocean glider but without wings, and with a lifetime of five or more years, measuring temperature and salinity.

NIWA vessels have deployed thousands of these floats over the last couple of decades. Argo is one of the most significant advances in our evidence base for understanding the ocean since the major World Ocean Circulation Experiment surveys of the 1990s

However, once on the continental shelf itself we have a new class of Argo to deploy – BGC Argo (BioGeoChemical). These are essentially gourmet Argo floats, with an enhanced range of sensors helping understand how the changing physics relates to biological parameters. I like to think of them as a multi-year “voyage in a can”. BGC Argo is expanding our evidence base for the changing ocean to include ecologically essential variables. In particular, ocean oxygen levels, one of the looming climate signals we need to keep an eye on.

My co-voyage lead, Dr. Denise Fernandez has been working for five years to get resources to deploy these complex drifting sentinels. The Antarctic Science Platform, through the efforts of Professors Nancy Bertler and Ian Hawes, acquired two of the floats for the ACTUATE voyage. Denise, with help from Australia’s Dr Christina Schallenberg (CSIRO) and the International Argo Programme, spent some time planning the mission for these two floats. It requires extra care when they are being deployed in shallow continental shelf waters. Even then, it was touch and go for delivery as timelines were really tight – but much to everyone’s relief the two floats arrived just in time to be tested and loaded onto the ship.

The ice shelf near Cape Crozier: Image Craig Stevens.

The BGC Argo are a step up in terms of cost, complexity and sensors from Core Argo - deployment for Core Argo is over in a flash as the crew are well-practised at getting them in the water. BGC Argo on the other hand are much heavier and delicate and require Denise follow a lengthy checklist before she gives the OK to the crew to deploy the float into the water.

None of these robots are replacing voyages like our ACTUATE expedition any time soon because of all the other sampling that goes on. However, they are providing a huge boost to the evidence-base for changes to the marine domain – especially in places and times that are hard to monitor like the ocean around Antarctica in winter.

With the overarching mission of the Antarctic Science Platform being to understand the impacts on Antarctica of greenhouse gas emissions, it is not lost on us that in doing so we too are burning fossil fuels. While we await the shift to low-carbon vessels, the main response we have as ocean scientists is the increased use of robotics and the better sharing of data.

On the ACTUATE voyage we expect to do around 50 CTD profiles. However, the combined number of profiles from our robotics will be in the order of 3,500 and so a massive reduction in costs and

emissions per profile. All these data will be openly available in many forms. After getting the last BGC Argo into the ocean, Denise did a 3am happy dance in the freezing cold. And from there we turned south again - next stop the Ross Ice Shelf itself - and *Tangaroa's* farthest south.

The Ross Ice Shelf – Feb 4

In 1841 when James Clark Ross, and his ships *Erebus* and *Terror*, sailed into what we now call the Ross Sea, he encountered the largest icebergs ever seen, the southern-most volcano and whales everywhere. These were things that, whilst remarkable, were at least known. What *was* literally off the charts was “the Barrier” - a 40 m high wall of ice that stretched so far east they went back to Hobart for winter before trying to find the other end.

By looking at the tabular bergs calving from the shelf they figured out that the barrier must be floating and probably several hundred metres thick. What they couldn't know though, was that it stretched back 800 km further south and held back a large part of the polar plateau – and its ability to raise sea level. They'd found the largest ice shelf on the planet.

The Ross Ice Shelf is a slab of ice with an area comparable to Spain and is wedged into a 750 km wide gap between Ross Island and the West Antarctic coast. Around a decade ago NIWA colleague Craig Stewart determined that the shelf around Ross Island was melting quite fast compared to the rest of the shelf. He had spent many summer seasons dropping off radar packages on the ice surface that could map ice melt on the underside. His data made it clear that warm water was sneaking into the ice shelf cavity along the eastern end of Ross Island - a place called Cape Crozier.

Cape Crozier is the location where three members of Scott's final expedition spent a winter looking for Emperor Penguin eggs prior to the ill-fated attempt on the South Pole the following summer. Our interest was a little more oceanic – we need to know what's forcing warm water into the cavity and will it accelerate if the oceans warm? And if warm water is going in – where is the balancing meltwater coming out?

Front of the Ross Ice Shelf: Image Craig Stevens/NIWA.

The ocean off Cape Crozier is where the Ross Sea Polynya forms every year. A polynya occurs when very cold winds blow off the Antarctic continent, making new sea ice but then immediately blowing the ice away. The new ice oozes out all the salt originally in the seawater so water beneath a polynya is cold, salty and oxygenated. It eventually goes on to refresh the entire ocean.

Back in 2018 when we were planning the first phase of the Antarctic Science Platform (ASP), we developed a concept to run a large ocean campaign to sample the Ross polynya in a programme dubbed **RISIPE** (Ross Ice Shelf Integrated Polynya Experiment). However, there wasn't an obvious vessel (at the time we thought sea ice and distance would put it beyond *Tangaroa's* operational limits) – and then Covid arrived putting plans on hold. It looked like we'd have to drop the whole idea.

However, in mid- 2023 the Antarctic Science Platform leadership - Professors Ian Hawes (Waikato) and Nancy Bertler (VUW/GNS) - developed an ambitious plan to fund a joint New Zealand – Italy voyage aboard the Italian ice breaker the *Laura Bassi*. So, this time last year, twelve of us, along with 25 Italian researchers, finally got to work in the region, and put some of the original RISIPE plan into action.

Despite the exceedingly short 2023 timeline we managed to scramble and put together 4 hydrographic moorings from the NIWA ocean moorings equipment pool – a nice demonstration of how the investment supports rapid response as delivery times on new gear is nudging six months. Then, thanks to the ASP-supported *Laura Bassi* expedition, we dropped them off in the ocean right in the critical zone near Cape Crozier. The opportunity came together so quickly we didn't even have a plan on how we'd get them back.

As it was, the Antarctic Science Platform (ASP) came aboard again, and so this year we are back to collect them, now aboard RV *Tangaroa*. In contrast to earlier *Tangaroa* voyages to the Ross Sea, ACTUATE includes a big loop down to the ice shelf front. From an Antarctic research perspective, this growth in oceanographic work reflects the importance of the Southern Ocean described in MFAT's strategy document described in an earlier update.

Collage used in post-voyage talks

Tangaroa is a fine ship, but it is not rated as an icebreaker able to break through sea ice, so we have to select the right conditions. Fortunately, things have been great (so far), so almost effortlessly we've taken the ship to its farthest south – and got our RISIPE moorings back.

“Mooring” is a little misleading as usually for oceanographic moorings there is nothing floating on the surface – it's all below, suspended by floats from a bottom weight. As *Tangaroa* came up to each mooring location, NIWA's Henk van Rossem would switch on an acoustic sonar modem to talk to the submerged equipment. Upon establishing contact he'd send a “release” signal, and the gear would drop a ballast weight and float up to the surface - at which point we'd be on hand to get the expensive gear, and even more importantly, the data, back aboard. Henk leads the deployments of the large

DART tsunami warning buoys spread around the Pacific Ocean, so he is well used to getting complex gear in and out of the ocean.

Perhaps most satisfyingly of all, one of the moorings that we got back had been set up to sample almost to the surface. This is because this is where meltwater is found, and where sea ice forms. We'd taken quite a risk with this, as any equipment at depths less than 300 m might get torn apart by one of the many ice bergs mooching around nearby. But we got away with it!

The data from this initial RISIPE campaign are going to be hugely influential in how the Antarctic Science Platform plans the next stage of work looking at how this large ice shelf is going to evolve with a warming ocean. With the instruments safely on board we headed west to the north coast of Ross Island for the last stop on our southern loop.

Ross Island and North – Feb 7

Last update saw us achieve *Tangaroa's* farthest south science where we recovered our RISIPE moorings from just a few kilometres north of the Ross Ice Shelf front. From there we headed west to a bay on the north side of Ross Island, nestled between Mounts Terror and Erebus, to set up for a benthic survey for a virtually unsampled location. The seafloor around the island is poorly mapped on the marine charts at the scale required for the sampling, so we spent the first part of our time there scanning the seafloor with a Multibeam Echosounder sonar.

This sonar technique uses a transducer in the ship's hull to map the seafloor in order to create high-resolution images for the science team to plan their sampling. In addition, it gives the ship's bridge officers confidence about the depth. NIWA's Alicia Maurice operates the seabed mapping controls, working out the best lines to survey and fine-tuning the sonar for the conditions, in order to build up a detailed picture of the seafloor. It all sounds easy but with our present mode of operation there's quite a bit of time-pressure. As soon as the new map emerged from Alicia's survey, the benthic sampling team were using it to target their upcoming sampling.

*Team gathers to watch the deep towed imaging system
Craig Stevens / NIWA*

One of the main tools for the benthic survey work doesn't take any physical samples at all. It is a towed camera system that gives the team real-time high-resolution video - NIWA's Deep Towed Imaging System (DTIS) has been evolving for different needs over the last 15 years. Its main advantage is it can be used to survey large seafloor areas quickly and, in a modestly priced package, provide high-resolution, geo-located imagery in a way that integrates with other data being collected. Jacob Hall and Nick Eton have been extending this bespoke technology as part of a development arc that stretches back to the first package developed in 2010 by oceanographic technologist Peter Hill.

A ship is constantly moving in the swell, and it is a lot of heavy machinery moving in different directions. And yet we scientists continually turn up with delicate instruments to get in the water! It's a credit to the ship's deck crew and Bridge officers that they find a method that works for everyone. Recent improvements to DTIS now make controlling the package much easier, with improved visual displays for the winch driver and camera operator, which in turn enables the video to get much closer to the seabed. At the same time, NIWA's recent investment in fibreoptic cable means that the imagery coming up the line has better clarity than ever. These cost-effective, behind the scenes, developments are among the many underpinning components making the voyage possible.

From the Ross Island site, we worked our way north over a week, and at each new site there was incredible scenery and also major surprises about seafloor species and abundance – and many happy scientists. Places ended up being described as *sea cucumber central*, *octopus heaven*, or the more straightforward *best place ever*. While locations like Ross Island and Coulman Island were new for our databases, other targets were in locations we'd sampled on previous voyages - like Cape Hallett. The repeat sampling is especially valuable to see how climate heating is affecting marine life in this part of New Zealand's ocean domain.

Cape Hallett, around 125 km south of Cape Adare on the northeast tip of the Victoria Land region, used to have a joint NZ-US research station up until the early 1970s. The Italian team we worked with last year (Pierpaolo Falco and others) have maintained a mooring and some sediment cores close by Hallett, in Edisto Inlet - and indeed as we were working, the *Laura Bassi* passed close-by to collect some instrumentation. It was a nice interlude to be exchanging WhatsApp messages with our friends and colleagues, at the same time as waving to them.

The Italian sediment work looks at evidence of the changing ice sheet over the last ten thousand years through to the present. This, in turn, forms the basis for a benthic ecosystem which has developed over that time to become the modern system we are cataloguing.

En route to Hallett we'd picked up our ocean glider *Manaia* who'd been working her way north over a ten-day period. It would have been nice to let her sample a little longer, but our schedule is a fine balance built around the drifting sea ice, the weather, and our looming departure deadline, and it doesn't take much for things to come unstuck.

Some of the amazing scientists onboard celebrating International Day of Women and Girls in Science – Image: Alina Madita Wiczorek / NIWA.

The glider pickup point was around 4 hours offshore, so we had to leave the stunning coastal scenery of Coulman Island behind and go on what seemed like a leap of faith to a GPS position sent out by a mostly submerged, two-metre-long tube, in a vast ocean. However, as we cautiously, lest we run her over, approached the mark, *Manaia* - with its yellow tail in a flat sea - turned out to be very easy to spot. A quick trip in the work boat for Dr Jasmin McInerney and crew, and we had our data-filled ocean robot back on board.

Manaia's mission was two-fold. Her data set will be used to help establish how water moves down the Drygalski Trough, with a focus mainly on the physical transformation that takes cold, salty, oxygen-rich water from coastal polynyas to the deep sea and exchanges with warmer waters offshore.

The second aspect the data will contribute to is new work looking to connect biology to physics in this unique environment. This work was initiated during the 2024 *Laura Bassi* joint Italy-New Zealand voyage where a collaboration between early career researchers from both nations was funded by MAC₃ Impact Philanthropies, in order to build their networks and profile.

For our 2025 *Tangaroa* ACTUATE voyage, NIWA provided Strategic Voyage Funds to enable Drs Alina Madita Wiczorek, Svenja Halfter and Jasmin McInerney, who had all been funded by Mac₃ – thanks again to the Antarctic Science Platform - to continue this work in order to cross disciplines and trophic scales by connecting physical water column structure and particulates from the glider, with acoustics, eDNA and net sampling. This type of interdisciplinary perspective will be fundamental to providing early awareness of large-scale biological changes forced by a warming climate.

Navigating the ice of Robertson Bay – image: Hugh Carter / Natural History Museum, London.

At this critical time for Aotearoa New Zealand's science sector, when both environmental systems and institutional structures are changing, it's more important than ever to support early career researchers (ECR). One of the many nice things about this voyage has been the demographic balance with the old hands and also ECR and students, some of whom will become tomorrow's leading researchers. This sense of positivity is added to with the science team's gender balance being 11f:9m, as well as Jenny, Marissa, Ninja, Erica and Jo on the ship's complement, all building on the sense that we are a future-facing enterprise.

From these coastal sites, we will move to deeper, more exposed waters to maintain some of our critical long-term ocean observing infrastructure.

The Troughs – Feb 11

If you look at a bathymetry chart of the Ross Sea continental shelf, it appears like a giant bear has clawed away at the seafloor. The complex coming and goings of the ice sheet in the region over the

last several thousand years has resulted in a number of north-south gouges. So, in the present day, we find a sequence of several, long, north-south troughs that act as passageways for water movement.

At the moment these passageways are important for two reasons. We know that cold, salty water, formed in polynyas, flows along the troughs to the open ocean - serving to oxygenate the oceans. There is evidence that the net oxygenating effect of this is changing rapidly. At the same time, we have hints that warm water to the north, sitting several hundred metres beneath the ocean surface, can, in places, be seen moving southward - also along these troughs, towards the Ross Ice Shelf itself. The ice is highly vulnerable to melting if this effect increases.

Understanding how these flows are changing with the last few decades of planetary warming is obviously important. However, it is also very beneficial to consider how the system behaved in previous geological times when atmospheric concentrations of CO₂ were along the lines of our present emissions trajectory. While it is not easy to bring together these two perspectives, we've embraced this in the Antarctic Science Platform as it's been something that I and Antarctic Science Platform co-PI Dr. Christina Riesselman (Univ. Otago) have guided our project team to look for linkages with processes ranging from tidal timescales (~24hr) to paleoclimate records going back 100 thousand years or more.

Clearly though, measuring what is going on in these troughs now is important. It is for these reasons, that New Zealand, along with groups from elsewhere have been trying to quantify the system. University of Auckland Associate Professor Melissa Bowen has been analysing these fluxes for close on a decade now, presently as part of the Antarctic Science Platform – and before that with the Deep South National Science Challenge. She's found the tides are a large factor in controlling the flow along the troughs, as well as identifying hints as to how flows move north and south along the troughs simultaneously.

In the same way we have an international team on board working on benthic sampling, we have a network off the ship equally invested in our progress. Along with our own efforts, teams from the Korean Polar Research Institute, Lamont Doherty Earth Observatory in the US, the University of Southampton in the U.K. and the Italian MORSea programme, have all come together to contribute in various ways – be it ship-time, instruments, or data analysis. The fact that there is so much international focus on this one region gives you a clear sense of its importance - ***this single modest channel has global implications.***

International research interest in the region is growing, not only from a climate perspective, but also the Ross Sea Marine Protected Area is a major stakeholder in what is being learned by this network and there are a growing number of requests reaching out to see how biological outcomes can be linked to this underpinning description of the system.

Of course, synthesizing such an observational network is not straightforward. Co-voyage leader Dr Denise Fernandez has been leading a process to design such a system that enables components to come and go as various funding streams and science priorities evolve. The next phase of the Antarctic Science Platform, starting later this year, will build upon this approach.

Aboard *Tangaroa* over the last couple of days we've been playing our part in this network by recovering and redeploying ocean monitoring instruments. It has meant we've kept a very close eye on the weather forecast, and the sea ice conditions, to find time windows that would work with the team on-board, whilst maximising other sampling. With a bit of zig-zagging we managed to recover and redeploy the instruments smoothly. The gear is a mix of precision, calibrated temperature and

salinity sensors, as well as current meters and oxygen sensors – maintained by NIWA and the University of Auckland.

Deploying a mooring- Image: Alina Madita Wieczorek / NIWA

This forms part of a de-centralised ocean observation system contribution that the Antarctic Science Platform has enabled, primarily with NIWA equipment plus some gear from Universities and the Antarctic Science Platform itself. The activity involves working with international colleagues to complement and share activities where we can. Just this season alone, the Korean *Araon* icebreaker deployed NZ instruments, *Tangaroa* deployed gear for US colleagues, the Italian ice breaker *Laura Bassi* is deploying moorings for us, and one of our research team will join the Chinese *Xue Long Two* icebreaker that will survey the region in March as sea ice reforms. All this makes clear that *Tangaroa's* efforts bring far more than just the data from the activity of the last month, but also it is a thread in an interweaving of international research priorities.

While the mooring operations proceeded in a very controlled fashion, I was having to keep my best poker-face and not ask for everyone to hurry up as we knew a

short, sharp southerly wind event was on its way. As we headed for Cape Adare and the shelter of Robertson Bay with the rising southerly behind, we look to see the state of sea ice at its entrance and if we can squeeze by to ride out the weather – and sample – near the largest Adelie penguin colony on the planet.

Cape Adare – Feb 14

The previous update came as we were scooting north to Cape Adare with a southerly storm *right* behind us. Cape Adare is at the northmost tip of the Transantarctic Mountains – a range that extends 3,500 km southwards, spanning Antarctica. It also serves to guide the winds of the Ross Sea along its west coast making for a tricky area to sample. However, just around the pointer-like tip of Cape Adare you enter the wedge-shaped Robertson Bay. In the right conditions it can prove a haven from the frequent storms – or, you can find yourself dodging swirls of sea ice.

As it was, after a little negotiation with the sea ice and icebergs at the entrance, we were able to get into a relatively ice-free part of the bay and carry on with benthic mapping and surveying. This made a useful balance to last time we were here in *Laura Bassi* when most of the sampling was for surface sediment. When not being blasted by wind, the bay is spectacular - ringed by mountains and

cascading glaciers. These have the strange effect of seeming both bigger and smaller in scale than many of the preceding coastal scenes.

Robertson Bay is notable in both human and ecological terms. It was the site of the first winter camp on Antarctica when, in 1899, Carsten Borchgrevink and team set up a base on a piece of flat ground near the bay entrance. Viewing a map, you can see why they chose the location as it looks sheltered from the worst of the southerly storms, but in fact the biggest of the storms just jump the local pass and bear down right on the flat

Glider retrieved safely – Image: Svenja Halfter / NIWA

beach area. Not only was it miserable in terms of weather, but Borchgrevink’s team also had to share the beach with roughly a million Adelie penguins, the largest such colony anywhere. I expect the novelty wore off for both groups.

After several days sampling the bay and, as the storm eased, the nearby Possession Islands, we headed eastward for our last work on the continental shelf and away from a remarkable sequence of views. One of our key work packages looks to combine eDNA, fisheries acoustics and zooplankton assemblages in a continuation of the work that Drs. Alina Madita Wieczorek and Svenja Halfter conducted at earlier stations. They are collaborating with Dr. Sherine Cubelio from India’s Centre for Marine Living Resources & Ecology which is part of India’s Ministry of Earth Sciences. Dr. Cubelio has joined us for her first Antarctic voyage to participate in work seeking to connect identification of higher trophic levels to ocean conditions. Sherine gave a talk onboard as part of our ship’s science seminar series and it was great to hear about the different types of ocean research work happening in India and the Indian Ocean. It is very exciting that this collaboration between India and Aotearoa New Zealand is growing as we all have a stake in the changes around Antarctica.

Alina, Svenja and Sherine’s work required a zig-zag path along the continental shelf edge looking for fish population areas between Cape Adare and Hallett Ridge. We’d seen some of the spectacular samples that were coming up in Svenja’s zooplankton nets, but this only just barely prepared us for the images of sea floor plants and animals captured by DTIS and its cameras. One of the angles that

Sunset over the Possession Islands –image: Svenja Halfter / NIWA

both Dr. Wieczorek's group, and the wider voyage, are working towards is stronger biophysical connections, so to conduct this work on the shelf-break edge makes a lot of sense. Certainly, from an empirical perspective the region has been a target for fishing – a sure indicator of high biological productivity. From a physical point of view there will be a good deal of mixing due to tides interacting with the shelf-break. But, most importantly, this is where we find the Antarctic Slope Current.

The Antarctic Slope Current is a westward flow found on all Antarctica's coastal margins. It is critical to the future of ice in Antarctica as it acts as a control on how warm water from further north finds its way south. We targeted this last year when we deployed three Argo floats, provided by the Canadian Argo team, across the slope current, well to the east of our present work. It is quite remarkable to see how far apart these three floats have ended up. This points to the complexity of the current, and the challenge for modelling approaches operating with little input data.

Whale fluke – Image: Svenja Halfter / NIWA

With all these processes going on, it was no surprise to see the range of species on DTIS cameras as we worked up submerged Hallett Ridge, 250 km to the east of Cape Adare. It's remarkable to be this far into a long trip and for people to still be excitedly hovering around the video monitors. Indeed, despite happening at midnight, the last DTIS video sampling run of the entire voyage seemed more like a party as the lab was crowded to the max with people, chocolates, streamers – and imagery of our polar marine environment. And so, from the tip of Hallett Ridge, we turned northwards.

Hometime – Feb 21

Our trip north was uneventful, if a little foggy and swelly. Happily, the Southern Ocean conditions were calm enough that we could even stop and take a CTD profile to the seabed in over 4.5 km of water. As well as this, *en route* we measured ocean surface and atmospheric data plus our trusty Continuous Plankton Recorder, all the way back home. We've worked out that we'd managed...

- Sampling Stations: 253
- CTD Conductivity-temperature-depth casts: 53
- CTD distance profiled: 29 km vertical
- Niskin water sample bottles: ~1100
- DTIS camera deployments: 72
- Sled tows: 13 deployed
- Sediment Grabs: 30 deployed
- Continuous Plankton Recorder tows: 7, for 2800 nautical miles
- Argo deployments: 12
- Rectangular Trawl (RMT): 10
- Zooplankton (Bongo) net tows: 12
- Hydrographic/biophysical moorings: 15
- Ocean Glider mission duration: 220 km with 180 science data profiles.
- Atmospheric and surface underway distance: > 4500 nautical miles

Wrap-up

So, what happens next? First off, we share the immediate data with the team, subject to initial QAQC. While a good number of papers and datasets will come out of this single voyage, the true power is in the intertwined value when the data add to the growing pool of information about the region.

This collective wisdom is growing because the area is important to a range of stakeholders. One way we can maximise this value is through the Southern Ocean Observing System (SOOS) – an international initiative that seeks to develop and share data from around Antarctica. This powerful focal point for collective science is required if we are going to have informed responses to the growing climate challenges.

It is fair to say that the set of shared experiences for everyone onboard will also prove invaluable in the future for collaboration and wider understanding of science.

As we come into port, I can finally own up that probably the most remarkable thing about the entire trip – other than the people, the science and the views – was the weather. Given that the ship is in very good order, our ability to work at such high latitudes is almost entirely governed by the wind, waves, and the cold. As it was, we won something like three lotteries in a row. I estimate we lost about two hours due to fog arriving at just the wrong time for a particular kind of sampling activity.

The locals – Image: Svenja Halfter / NIWA

For every other *Tangaroa* Ross Sea voyage you would have added – “and sea ice” to the list of challenges. While it did affect some of our work, it was only a few days where we found our sampling needed to adapt to drifting patches of ice. This was in part made possible thanks to improved data and models (with interpretation from Evan Solly the ice pilot), and the ability to easily access them via a decent internet link. However, it was also due the stark reduction in sea ice in the region. Sure, it might prove that it was

“just a low ice year”, but there really wasn’t much around and all the evidence points to this continuing.

This need to understand a system under pressure is why this work is supported. The sea days are funded by MBIE’s *Tangaroa* Reference Group. We acknowledge the continued support from the Antarctic Science Platform through the efforts of Professors Nancy Bertler and Ian Hawes with assistance from Mel Climo and Anne-Marie Rowe. NIWA provided substantial funding through its SSIF Strategic Voyage Fund and CAPEX equipment funding programme - with thanks to Drs Mike Williams and Joshu Mountjoy.

Scientifically, we have a whole cohort of colleagues working behind the scenes - Drs. Vonda Cummings, Nathan Kenny, Holly Winton, Kathy Gunn, Phil Sutton, Assoc. Prof. Melissa Bowen, Prof. Jan Strugnell, Prof. Chris Zappa, and Assoc. Prof. Stefano Schiaparelli. Then we have the amazing researchers on board – Prof. Miles Lamare, Drs. Ira Cooke, Nicole Hill, Alina Madita Wieczorek, Svenja Halfter, Gert-Jan Jeunen, Hugh Carter - with additional support from Marco Grillo, Emma Downer and Fiona Schultz.

Thanks go to the ship's Master Mapu Jr Tapua'i, and the bridge team Ian, Marissa and Ninja, for running a fantastic voyage. Everyone aboard played a part in the success – the engineers Rob, Petro and Ragin, and the galley/steward team - Steve, Grant and Jo. And a special thanks to the deck teams who were out there in all Antarctica's weather, with winches, nets and cables – Glen, Shane, Bruce, Jordan, Erica and Callum. The ice pilot, Evan Solly, helped navigate the challenging seas and the ship's Doctor Dr. Jenny Visser was a fount of knowledge, doing far more than only looking after our physical well-being. NIWA Vessels' Wellington-based team – Simon Wadsworth, Karen Keddy, Sol Fergus, Ross Mitchell, as well as Dave, Brian and many others, got us off the wharf – and will be there to greet us.

Denise and I would like to emphasise that the success of the science was made possible by a combination of the skilled, experienced people on shore and on the ship. The complexity of this endeavour means you can't just turn up and expect things to work – it requires trained professionals with a can-do attitude. Dr Jasmin McInerney, Nick Eton, Dr Pame Olmedo-Rojas, Jacob Hall, Henk van Rossem and Alicia Maurice on board and Dr Sadie Mills, Dr Stacy Deppeler, Eleanor Haigh, Dr. Craig Stewart, Cassandra Elmer and Andrew Marriner back at the NIWA Wellington laboratories, were the real secret to succeeding at 76 South.

In addition, if people don't know about the science and the world about them, then the impact of all this effort falls short. A huge thanks for the science communication effort goes to the indefatigable Ryan Willoughby and his colleagues at NIWA, Antarctica NZ and other institutes around the world. With WhatsApp being a key piece of communication around the ship, Ryan was in on the chat from the first to last with advice, requests, encouragement, suggestions etc.

Sea stars sorted from one of the first collections – Image: Alina Madita Wieczorek / NIWA

I'll finish up this log by describing our last CTD profile of the entire voyage – well north of Antarctica and the Polar Front. I'd dragged myself out of my bunk for the final 5 am profile. Denise was already hard at work in the hydro-lab and with great satisfaction, pointed to the data screen for the CTD as it neatly traced out a text-book example of Antarctic Bottom Water silently flowing four kilometres beneath us - working its way around the planet. This layer of cold, salty, oxygenated water is an essential part of how our planet presently works. Despite being two thousand kilometres from the likely formation point where we'd sampled only a few weeks previously - here

was clear evidence of Antarctica's reach, as the water mass headed north to Aotearoa and beyond – and it is changing.

Team Success and Development

The success of any voyage relies on the people – something that is dramatically amplified on long voyages. A lot of effort went into looking after the team - and the team put a lot of energy into doing their part to make it a success.

Onboard Science Talks

- Craig Stevens on geography/history
- Hugh Carter on starfish
- Ira Cooke on sexy octopus
- Hugh Carter on history footage
- Jenny Visser on travel medicine
- Hana Ishii on paleo/atmos
- Craig Stevens on cavities
- Svenja Halfter on sea ice phyto
- Sherine Cubelio on CMLRE/India
- Miles Lamarre on cryo fish
- Nicole Hill on biodiversity tools and outcomes
- Jasmin McInerney on gliders
- Fiona Schultz (Southern Ocean) & Marco Grillo (species ID and photography)
- Emma Downer (eDNA shellfish etc) & Marco (samples and biodiversity)
- Alina Madita Wieczorek on fish & eDNA & Jacob on DTIS
- Pame Olmedo-Rojas's career & development in Chile

Dr. Jasmin McInerney giving one of the science talks – Image Craig Stevens.

Crossing the Line Ceremony

The past voyages have had a tradition of a “crossing the line” ceremony. Somewhat anomalously it is for crossing 60°S and not the Antarctic Circle. Nonetheless all those who had not travelled south previously were awarded a certificate and there were costumes.

Some of the costumes for the 60°S crossing the line.

Image of the week

The images being circulated on the ship via WhatsApp were visible to the Comms team in Wellington and every week Ryan would select a winner of “image of the week” that would be awarded during one of the regular science meetings. Occasionally there were tied awards.

**IMAGE OF THE WEEK: WEEK TWO
TAN2502 ACTUATE VOYAGE
HENK VAN ROSSEM**

Example "image of the week".

Acknowledgements

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A team effort. Image - Alina Madita Wieczorek / NIWA.

References

Fernandez, Stevens et al. Spatiotemporal connections in the Ross Sea: A synthesis from the New Zealand Antarctic Science Platform Ocean Mechanics project. *Elementa: Science of the Anthropocene* 2025; 13 (1): 00097. doi:

<https://doi.org/10.1525/elementa.2024.00097>

Stevens C and Fernandez D. 2024. Aotearoa New Zealand Developments in Ocean Science in the Ross Sea – from the Southern Ocean to the Ice Shelf Grounding Line. *CLIVAR Exchanges Special Issue - Highlighting Ocean Research, Data and Networks of Antarctic Programs*, 83, 30-35. <https://www.clivar.org/documents/exchanges-83>